

The Enzymes in Snake-venom. Part I. Their Action on Hæmoglobin and on Protein Solutions of Different p_{H} .

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It has been recorded by several early investigators that venoms of many poisonous snakes can exert marked digestive action (in *vivo*) on animal tissues. Later on, this effect was found to be produced by some proteolytic enzymes present in the venom. Flexner and Noguchi (*Univ. Pennsylv. Med. Bull.*, 1902, **15**, 345), Delezenne (*Compt. rend.*, 1902, **135**, 329), Noc (*Ann. Inst. Pasteur*, 1904, **18**, 387), Launoy (*Compt. rend.*, 1902, **135**, 401), and Housey and Negrete (*Rev. Del. Inst. Bact. Buenos-Aires*, 1918, **1**, 341) observed that snake venom can hydrolyse proteins like gelatin, albumin, casein etc. Using casein and serum albumin as substrates, Launoy (*loc. cit.*) observed that with the venoms of cobra and of the vipera, the proteolysis stops when albumose is formed. It does not proceed so far as to form peptone. Recently Dunn (*J. Pharm. Exp. Therap.*, 1934, **50**, 386) noticed that venom of *Crotaius adamantus* can digest casein suspended in 0.2 N-sodium acetate more rapidly than casein of coagulated milk without the sodium acetate. It may be pointed out that the influence of the reaction of the medium on the activity of the enzymes (in snake-venom) has not been studied by any of the authors already mentioned. It is now recognised that proteases of animal origin can be separated into three groups, based on their activity in media of different p_{H} :

(i) The proteases which are active in distinctly acid range are analogous to pepsin.

(ii) Those which are active in the slightly alkaline range with an optimum at about p_{H} 8, are similar to trypsin.

(iii) Those which show optimum activity in the neighbourhood of p_{H} 5 are analogous to kathepsin.

It will be interesting to know to which of these groups the proteases in snake-venom belong. In the present paper the results obtained by studying the action of venoms of cobra (*Naja Naja*) and of Russell's viper on hæmoglobin and of cobra-venom on different proteins in media of different p_{H} values have been recorded.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Action of Cobra-venom on Proteins.

Stock solution of gelatin (5%), Merck's dried egg-albumin and casein were prepared in physiological saline (0.85% NaCl). The solutions were prepared the day before they were required for use and kept in a refrigerator at 4° with the addition of a few drops of toluene. The gelatin used was previously purified by electro dialysis. The casein solution was prepared by dissolving it in NaOH and then nearly neutralising the solution with dilute HCl.

A solution of cobra-venom (1%) in physiological saline was prepared a few hours before it was required for use. Its toxicity was tested by intramuscular injection into pigeons. It was found that 0.4 mg. of venom (dry weight) just kills a pigeon weighing between 300 to 320 g.

The extent of hydrolysis was followed by Willistätter's method of titration in 90% alcoholic solution with alcoholic caustic potash, using thymolphthalein as an indicator.

The p_{H} of the reaction media was maintained nearly constant by adding buffer solutions. Between p_{H} 2 to 5, citrate buffers were used and between p_{H} 6 to 9.6 phosphate and borate buffers were used. The stock protein solution (20 c.c.) were taken in an Erlenmeyer's flask and its p_{H} adjusted to the requisite volume by adding a few drops of NaOH or HCl solution according to need. To this solution, 10 c.c. of buffer solution of the same p_{H} were added. 10 C.c. of this buffered protein solution were placed in each of the two conical flasks. To one of the flasks, 2 c.c. of the solution and 8 c.c. of physiological saline were added. To the other flask which served as a control, 8 c.c. of physiological saline and 2 c.c. of the cobra-venom solution were added; the latter was previously heated for 50 minutes at 75°, to destroy the proteases present in it. To each of the flasks a few drops of toluene were added to prevent bacterial growth and they were placed in a thermostat at 35°. After suitable intervals of time, 5 c.c. portions of the solution were withdrawn and added to 45 c.c. of absolute alcohol to which 0.5 c.c. of 0.5% thymolphthalein solution in alcohol were previously added. The mixture was then immediately titrated with alcoholic potash. In another set of control experiments 10 c.c. of the buffered protein solution were mixed with 10 c.c. of 0.85% NaCl and incubated at 35°. After suitable intervals of time,

5 c.c. portions of this solution were titrated in the manner described above ; but just before titration 0.5 c.c. of 1% cobra-venom solution was added to it. The two sets of control experiments were in satisfactory agreement with each other. The results obtained are recorded below. As the proteolytic power of the venom was found to be weak, the interval of time allowed for digestion was 24 hours. The action of trypsin on casein media of different p_{H} values was also studied for the purpose of comparison and the data are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE I.

Substrate used—gelatin.

p_{H} .	N/25-alcoholic KOH required to titrate		Diff. between columns 2 & 3.
	Active venom and substrate.	Control.	
2.0	6.60 c.c.	6.60 c.c.	0
4.0	4.20	4.25	-0.05
5.0	3.85	3.80	+0.05
5.5	3.65	3.50	+0.15
6.0	3.30	3.00	+0.30
7.0	3.10	2.60	+0.50
7.4	2.95	2.40	+0.55
7.8	2.80	2.20	+0.60
8.4	2.45	1.90	+0.55
9.0	2.10	1.70	+0.40

TABLE II.

Substrate used—egg-albumin.

p_{H} .	N/25-alcoholic KOH required to titrate		Diff. between columns 2 & 3.
	Active venom and substrate.	Control.	
6.0	3.30 c.c.	3.00 c.c.	0.30
7.0	2.98	2.50	0.48
8.0	2.65	2.10	0.55
9.2	2.00	1.60	0.40

TABLE III.

p_{H}	Substrate used—casein. Temp. of bath, 37°.		Diff. between columns 2 & 3.
	<i>N</i> /25-alcoholic KOH required to titrate Active venom and substrate	Control.	
6.0	3.55 c.c.	3.00 c.c.	0.55
6.4	3.52	2.85	0.67
7.0	3.20	2.50	0.70
8.2	2.80	2.15	0.65
9.0	2.25	1.65	0.60

TABLE IV.

Substrate—casein. Enzyme—trypsin.
20 C c. of the reaction mixture contained 2 c c. of 0.25% trypsin soln.

p_{H}	<i>N</i> /25-alcoholic KOH required to titrate		Diff. between columns 2 & 3.
	Trypsin and casein.	Control	
5.5	4.15 c.c.	3.50 c.c.	0.65
6.6	4.25	2.90	1.35
7.6	3.60	2.45	1.15
8.6	2.80	1.80	1.00

It will be noticed from Fig. 1. and also from the data given in the tables that with gelatin and egg-albumin as substrate, the proteolytic enzyme in cobra-venom has its optimum activity at p_{H} 8 or near about it, while with the casein as substrate, the optimum activity of the enzyme is in the neighbourhood of p_{H} 6.6. The results are in agreement with the action of trypsin on these substrates as observed by Long and Hull (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 1051). There is, however, some doubt as to the p_{H} of casein suspension at which trypsin possesses its optimum activity. According to Cole ("Practical Physiological Chemistry," 1928, p. 226) with casein also, the optimum activity of trypsin is in the neighbourhood of p_{H} 8.0 and not 6.6. The action of trypsin on casein suspension was, therefore, studied by

the author and the results obtained are recorded in Table IV. The data show that the optimum activity is near about p_H 6.6. It may, therefore, be concluded that as far as the dependence of activity on the reaction of the substrate solution is concerned, the behaviour of the protease in cobra-venom is similar to that of trypsin. Further work in this line with venoms of cobra and of other snakes are in progress.

FIG. 1.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to gelatin, egg-albumin and casein.

Action of Venoms of Cobra and of Russell's Viper on Hæmoglobin.

In the postmortem examination of the victims of snake-bite, it has been observed by several workers that the blood appeared somewhat dark. To obtain further information on this point, the action of snake-venom on hæmoglobin was studied. A thick suspension (0.4 c.c.) of red blood corpuscles of horse was added to 4 c.c. of sterilised distilled water, whereby the corpuscles were hæmolyzed. Hæmoglobin solution (1 c.c.) was poured to each of the three test tubes. To one

of these tubes, 1 c.c. of an 1% cobra-venom solution and to another 1 c.c. of an 1% Russell's viper-venom were added. To the third tube, which served as control, one c.c. of 0.85% NaCl was added. After 16 hours, the contents of the tubes were suitably diluted and examined spectroscopically. Distinct absorption band of methæmoglobin at $630 \mu\mu$ in the red was noticed in the two tubes treated respectively with venoms of cobra and of Russel's viper. The control did not show any such band. It is thus evident that these venoms contain either an oxidising agent similar to $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ or an enzyme which can cause the oxidation of hæmoglobin to methæmoglobin.

SUMMARY.

1. With gelatin and egg-albumin as substrates the protease in cobra-venom was found to possess its optimum activity between p_H 7.8 to 8.0.

2. With casein as substrate the optimum activity of trypsin as also of the protease in cobra-venom was found to be in the neighbourhood of p_H 6.6.

3. The venoms of cobra and of Russell's viper can bring about the oxidation of hæmoglobin to methæmoglobin.

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